

Studying Civil Suits Commenced Arising Out Of Assault and Custodial Death in Malaysia

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Abstract: *When assault and death in custody had occurred, and the evidence strongly suggests that the assault and death are caused by police brutality, the wrongful exercise of their powers, or negligence, then the family members are entitled to sue the police officer and government over the assault and custodial death. In this article, the writer will study the civil suit commenced arising out of assault and custodial death by exploring the causes of action, assessment of damages, proceedings against government and judicial responses in this area.*

Keywords: *Assault, Custodial Deaths, Cause of Action, Damages, Judicial Trends*

1. INTRODUCTION

Assault and custodial death due to misfeasance by the police have always been a controversial topic in Malaysia. In regard to custodial death, there have been many cases of custodial deaths reported in Malaysia from previous years. More recent cases of custodial death due to misfeasance by the police, such as *Kugan's case* and *Chandran a/l Perumal's case* have captured the public's attention. Generally, the suspect and surviving family members have the right to commence a civil suit seeking damages from the police officer and government over the assault and custodial death. The causes of action for assault and death in custody lie in tort.

2. CAUSE OF ACTION

A cause of action is important to a civil suit, without which a civil suit cannot arise. There are a number of specific causes of action in assault and custodial death cases, including the tort of negligence, misfeasance of the public office, and trespass to the person (assault and battery). To succeed in his claim, the Plaintiff must prove the elements of that cause of action. The specific causes of action in assault and custodial death cases are as follows:

2.1 Tort of Negligence

In essence, the tort of negligence is concerned with the legal liability and consequences generally arising from negligent conduct, that is, conduct falling below the standard expected of a reasonable person. The legal requirement necessary for the plaintiff to establish an action in the tort of negligence is that he must first establish the existence of a duty of care owed by the defendant to the plaintiff. Secondly, the defendant must have breached this duty of care to the plaintiff and thirdly, the defendant's breach must have caused the damage suffered by the plaintiff (Gary Chan Kok Yew and Lee Pey Woan, 2016).

The landmark decision on the tort of negligence in England was none other than the case of *Donoghue v Stevenson [1932] AC 562*. In this case, the friend of a purchaser of a bottle of ginger beer that contained the decomposed remains of a dead snail had suffered gastro-enteritis upon consuming the contents. There was no contractual relationship between the consumer and the manufacturer. Nonetheless, a claim for personal injury under the tort of negligence was brought by the ultimate consumer of the ginger beer against the manufacturer. With regard to the duty of care issue, Lord Atkin proceeded to outline the "neighbor principle" as follows:

"You must take reasonable care to avoid acts or omissions which you can reasonably foresee would be likely to injure your neighbour...persons who are so closely and directly affected by my act that I ought reasonably to have them in contemplation as being so affected when I am directing my mind to the acts and omissions which are called in question."

The police have a duty of care to prevent harm to persons in custody, in both common law and statute. In Malaysia, the Court of Appeal in the case of *Datuk Seri Khalid Abu Bakar & Ors v N Indra Nallathamby & Another [2014] 9 CLJ 15* made the following pronouncements on the duty of care of the police authorities in a case of death of a detainee whilst in police custody:

".....The police force is a public professional body and as in other professional bodies there exist duties of care in the discharge of their powers. In the context of the police force, it is their standard operating procedure (SOP), and that should be subject to scrutiny by the court of law. As to what that duty of care and standard of care depends on the circumstances of each individual case and it is for the courts to determine what that duty and standard of care are as was done in the Federal Court case of Foo Fio Na v. Dr. Soo Fook Mun & Anor [2007] 1 CLJ 229; [2007] 1 MLJ 593."

In *Foo Fio Na's case*, the Federal Court quoted with approval Callaghan J in *Hajgato v London Health Association et al. (1982) 36 OR (2d) 669*, wherein action in negligence in respect of personal injuries sustained during post-operative case the learned judge stated as follows:

"In my view, however, a court has a right to strike down substandard approved practices when common sense dictates such a result. No profession is above the law, and the courts on behalf of the public have a critical role to play in monitoring and precipitating changes where required in professional standards."

At common law, the police have a negative duty to avoid causing harm to detainees. At the same time, they also have positive duties to ensure:

- (a) that the detainee does not harm himself (*Howard v Jarvis (1958) 98 CLR 177*);
- (b) that the detainee is not harmed (*Reeves v Commissioner of Police of the Metropolis [2000] 1 AC 360*);
- (c) that the detainee is not harmed by other detainees (*R (Amin) v Secretary of State for the Home Department [2004] 1 AC 653*);
- (d) that the detainee is given proper medical care and attention (*Selvi a/p Narayan & Anor (joint administrator for the estate and dependant of Chandran a/l Perumal, deceased) v Koperal Zainal bin Mohd Ali & Ors [2017] 9 MLJ 300*).

The police also have statutory duties to ensure the safety of the detainees in the police custody. Specific statutory duties arising under the Lock-Up Rules 1953. For instance, the Officer-in-Charge has a duty to report any apparent mental disorder, injury, or illness to the Medical Officer without delay (Rule 36), and to inspect all parts of each lock up at least once a day and see every prisoner confined at least once in every twenty-four hours and visit each lockup at an uncertain hour of the night at least once in every seven days. (Rule 35 (1)). The Lock-Up Rules 1953 are a complete code which governs the handling and management of detainees. The rationale for imposing on the police such a statutory duty of care is that the police has deprived the detainee of his liberty and taken full control over him.

2.2 Misfeasance of the public office

The claim of public misfeasance is a tortious claim. It is a public law tort in that it can only be committed by public officers exercising their powers wrongly resulting in injury to the claimant. The rationale behind this tort was aptly put by Lord Bingham in *Watkins v Secretary of State for the Home Department and others [2006] 2 AC 395*:

"There is a great force in the Plaintiff's submission that is where a public officer knowingly and deliberately acts in breach of his lawful duty he should be amenable to a civil action at the suit of anyone who suffers at his hands. There is an obvious public interest in bringing public servants guilty of outrageous conduct to book. Those who act in such a way should not be free to do so with impunity."

In order for the Plaintiff to sustain a claim of public misfeasance, he is required to prove the elements as set out in the case of *Three Rivers District Council v Bank of England [2003] 2 AC 1*, which are as follows:

- (a) *the act complained of had been committed by a public officer purportedly pursuant to the exercise of his public power;*
- (b) *the act committed must be done with malice which Lord Steyn in Three Rivers explained as follows:*

First, there is the case of targeted malice by a public officer, i.e., conduct specially intended to injure a person or persons. This type of case involves bad faith in the sense

of the exercise of public power for an improper or ulterior motive. The second form is where a public officer acts knowing that he has no power to do the act complained of and that the act probably injures the plaintiff. It involves bad faith inasmuch as the public officer does not have an honest belief that his act is unlawful

- (c) *that there is proximity between the deceased and the defendants giving rise to the plaintiff a legal standing to sue; and*
- (d) *that the acts of the defendants had caused material damage to the deceased.”*

2.3 Assault and battery

An assault is an act of the defendant which directly and intentionally causes the plaintiff to reasonably apprehend the imminent infliction of a battery. For an assault to occur, the plaintiff must reasonably apprehend actual physical contact at the time the threat was made. The test for “reasonable apprehension” is an objective one. It is based on what a reasonable person in the shoes of the plaintiff knows or would be expected to know in the circumstances of the particular case (Gary Chan Kok Yew and Lee Pey Woan, 2016).

On another hand, the battery is a trespass to the person consisting of an intentional act that directly causes a physical interference with the body of the plaintiff, without lawful justification or the plaintiff’s consent. The defendant must intend to apply force against the plaintiff, but need not intend to harm or injure the plaintiff. A hostile motive is generally not required, but in cases of trivial interference, it helps to establish the absence of the plaintiff’s consent. According to the House of Lords in *Collins v Wilcock [1984] 1 WLR 1172*, a battery is actionable ‘per se’ without proof of damage (Lexis Malaysia, 2017).

In short, battery requires an actual application of force on the plaintiff, whilst assault is a threat of force on the plaintiff. In tort law, battery and assault are intentional torts that involve “unwanted touching.”

3. ASSESSMENT OF DAMAGES

As regards tortious acts and/or omissions which cause the death of the victim, the common law does not confer any remedy upon the estate of the deceased person or upon others adversely affected by the death of the victim. Legislative intervention in England changed the legal position in two significant ways. Firstly, a new cause of action in favour of certain dependents of the deceased person was introduced under the Fatal Accidents Act 1846. Secondly, the rule that cause of action will no longer expire with the deceased victim but will vest in his estate was enacted into law in the Law Reform (Miscellaneous Provisions) Act 1934 (Lim Heng Seng, 1995).

Malaysian legislation to the same effect is modelled along the lines of the legislation in England. The Fatal Accidents Act 1976 is similar to section 7 of the Civil Law Act, whereas section 1(1) of the Law Reform (Miscellaneous Provisions) Act 1934 is similar to section 8 of the Civil Law Act. Section 7 of the Civil Law Act provides for the compensation to the family of a person for loss occasioned by his death. The relevant provisions state that:

“(1) Whenever the death of a person is caused by wrongful act, neglect or default, and the act, neglect or default is such as would, if death had not ensued, have entitled the party injured to maintain an action and recover damages in respect thereof, the party who would have been liable if death had not ensued shall be liable to an action for damages, notwithstanding the death of the person injured, and although the death has been caused under such circumstances as amount in law to an offense under the Penal Code.

(2) Every such action shall be for the benefit of the wife, husband, parent, and child, if any, of the person whose death has been so caused and shall be brought by and in the name of the executor of the person deceased.”

Section 8 (1) of the Civil Law Act provides the effect of death on a certain cause of action.

“(1) Subject to this section, on the death of any person all causes of action subsisting against or vested in him shall survive against, or, as the case may be, for the benefit of, his estate:

Provided that this subsection shall not apply to causes of action for defamation or seduction or for inducing one spouse to leave or remain apart from the other or to any claim for damages on the ground of adultery.”

Once the damage is held to have been caused by the tortfeasor’s wrongful act or omission and liability for negligence is held to exist, the focus will shift to the remedy which the law makes available to the person wronged. It is known as an award of damages.

To discuss what sort of damages can be claimed and the amount of award granted by court, comparison will be made based on the previous cases of *Datuk Seri Khalid bin Abu Bakar & Ors v N Indra a/p P Nallathamby (the administrator of the estate and dependent of Kugan a/l Ananthan, deceased) and another appeal [2015] 1 MLJ 353*, *Selvi a/p Narayan & Anor (joint administrator for the estate and dependant of Chandran a/l Perumal, deceased) v Koperal Zainal bin Mohd Ali & Ors [2017] 9 MLJ 300* and *Suzana bt Md Aris (claiming as administrator of the estate and a dependant of Mohd Anuar bin Sharip, deceased) v DSP Ishak bin Hussain & Ors [2011] 1 MLJ 107*. The table of comparison is shown as follows:

Damages awarded (RM)	A. Kugan	P. Chandran	Mohd Anuar bin Sharip
Loss of support/ dependency	192,000	144,000	472,000
Bereavement	-	10,000	10,000
Funeral expenses	9,700	-	3,000
Other special damages	-	3,500	-
Pain and suffering	50,000	-	2,220
Misfeasance of public office	50,000		
Aggravating factors	-	-	50,000
Aggravated damages	-	-	500,000
Exemplary damages	300,000	200,000	500,000

The various heads of damages for personal injury resulting in death will be briefly explained below:

3.1 Loss of support

In *Chan Chin Ming & Anor v Lim Yok Eng [1994] 3 MLJ 233*, Peh Swee Chin SCJ succinctly explained the loss of support as financial loss sustained by a dependant. His lordship further explained that under section 7 of the Civil Law Act 1956, the persons entitled to claim such loss of support in respect of a deceased person are the wife, husband, parent and child only, not including a brother or a sister. In other words, a plaintiff can only claim in such a case for financial loss which he sustains as a dependant and not in any other way.

To determine the loss of support, the procedure is contained in section 7 (3) (iv) of the Civil Law Act 1956, which sets out as follows:

“(3) The damages which the party who shall be liable under subsection (1) to pay to the party for whom and for whose benefit the action is brought shall, subject to this section, be such as will compensate the party for whom and for whose benefit the action is brought for any loss of support suffered together with any reasonable expenses incurred as a result of the wrongful act, neglect or default of the party liable under subsection (1):

Provided that –

(i) ;

(ii) ;

(iii) ;

(iv) in assessing the loss of earnings in respect of any period after the death of a person where such earnings provide for or contribute to the damages under this section the Court shall -

(a) take into account that where the person deceased has attained the age of fifty five years at the time of his death, his loss of earnings for any period after his death shall not be taken into consideration; and in the case of any other person deceased, his loss of earnings for any

period after his death shall be taken into consideration if it is proved or admitted that the person deceased was in good health but for the injury that caused his death and was receiving earnings by his own labour or other gainful activity prior to his death;

(b) take into account only the amount relating to the earnings as aforesaid and the Court shall not take into account any prospect of the earnings as aforesaid being increased at any period after the person's death;

(c) take into account any diminution of any such amount as aforesaid by such sum as is proved or admitted to be the living expenses of the person deceased at the time of his death;

(d) take into account that in the case of a person who was of the age of thirty years and below at the time of his death, the number of years' purchase shall be 16; and in the case of any other person who was of the age range extending between thirty one years and fifty four years at the time of his death, the number of years' purchase shall be calculated by using the figure 55, minus the age of the person at the time of death and dividing the remainder by the figure 2."

3.2 Bereavement

In the event of death, a claim for bereavement expenses may be made for the benefit of certain dependants. As stated in *Tan Harry v Teo Chee Yeow Aloysius [2004] 1 SLR (R) 513*, any benefit accruing to a dependant by reason of the death has to be deducted from the dependency claim except for certain specified sums. However, if the dependants would eventually have inherited the money or assets, the deduction should not be made. In *Ling Kee Ling v Leow Leng Siong [1994] 3 SLR (R) 395*, in assessing the claim of any dependant, the relationship between the deceased and the dependant, the personal circumstances of the deceased and the dependant, such as age, occupation, financial means and needs, and marital status, have to be considered in order to determine what the reasonable expectations would be (Gary Chan Kok Yew and Lee Pey Woan, 2016).

3.3 Special damages

Special damages such as loss of earnings or profits, medical expenses, nursing care, loss of pension rights and transportation expenses that have been reasonably incurred may be recovered. These special damages are required to be specifically pleaded and strictly proven (Gary Chan Kok Yew and Lee Pey Woan, 2016).

3.4 Pain and suffering

Damages for pain and suffering are awarded for both future pain and suffering as well as for what has already been endured by the Plaintiff. In order to claim for pain and suffering, the plaintiff had to be conscious at the relevant time of the accident. The quantum of the award would depend on various factors, such as the plaintiff's awareness of the pain, his capacity for suffering, the extent of the pain and whether the pain was temporary or permanent (Gary Chan Kok Yew and Lee Pey Woan, 2016).

3.5 Vindictory damages

One purpose of tort law is to allow an aggrieved party to vindicate his or her rights via the legal process. In exceptional circumstances, an award of damages may be seen as vindicating an infringed constitutional right, though in combination with other rationales for the award. In *Attorney General of Trinidad and Tobago v Ramanoop [2006] 1 AC 328*, the Privy Council opined that:

"The fact that the right violated was a constitutional right adds an extra dimension to the wrong. An additional award, not necessarily of substantial size, may be needed to reflect the sense of public outrage, emphasize the importance of the constitutional right and the gravity of the breach, and deter further breaches."

Nevertheless, the majority of the UK Supreme Court rejected the grant of an additional award of vindictory damages. Lord Dyson in the case of *R v Secretary of State for the Home Department [2011] 2 WLR 671*, cautioned that "undesirable uncertainty" would ensue if vindictory damages were to be awarded and

referred to it as “an unruly horse.” His Lordship opined that the purpose of vindicating a claimant’s common law rights would be fulfilled by an award of compensatory damages including nominal damages where no substantial loss is proved or alternatively, exemplary damages if the requirements are met (Gary Chan Kok Yew and Lee Pey Woan, 2016).

3.6 Aggravated Damages

Aggravated damages may be awarded for the additional injury suffered by the plaintiff arising from the manner and motives of the defendant’s commission of the tort or his subsequent conduct. The award is for additional injury to feelings and the mental distress caused to the plaintiff.

The purpose of an award of aggravated damages is to compensate the victim for the injury suffered, not to punish the wrongdoer. Due to the additional injuries suffered by the plaintiff, the basic award of damages may not suffice to compensate the plaintiff, hence the need to award aggravated damages.

In order to establish a claim for aggravated damages, a causal connection between the exceptional or contumelious conduct of a defendant and the injury to feelings suffered by the plaintiff is required (Gary Chan Kok Yew and Lee Pey Woan, 2016).

3.7 Exemplary damages

The main rationale for an award of exemplary damages is deterrence. The House of Lords in the landmark decision in *Rookes v Barnard [1964] AC 1129* outlined two main categories of cases where exemplary or punitive damages may be awarded:

- (a) oppressive, arbitrary or unconstitutional actions by the servants of the Government; or
- (b) the defendant’s conduct has been calculated by him to make a profit for himself which exceeds the compensation payable.

Although section 8(2) of the Civil Law Act 1956 prohibits exemplary damages to be recovered by the estate of a deceased person, but the Court of Appeal in the case of *Datuk Seri Khalid bin Abu Bakar & Ors v N Indra a/p P Nallathamby (the administrator of the estate and dependent of Kugan a/l Ananthan, deceased) and another appeal [2015] 1 MLJ 353* has held that where there is a breach of a constitutional right by a public authority, section 8(2) of the Civil Law Act does not apply and the courts cannot be barred from awarding exemplary damages. Section 8 of the Civil Law Act only applies to private torts in so far as the prohibition of awarding exemplary damages is concerned.

4. PROCEEDINGS AGAINST GOVERNMENT

It has been accepted for many centuries that the government in its personal capacity is immune from any wrong, be it criminal or civil suits. This aspect of the Constitution found expression in such ancient legal maxims and principles as 'the King can do no wrong' and 'the King cannot be sued in his own courts.' However, as time goes by, the above doctrines have been eroded as more and more cases involving the government comes before the court of law. Furthermore, some countries, to a certain extent, have forfeited the protective veils that grant immunity towards the government. Consequently, the government has to be answerable for its conducts in the administration of the country (Mahyuddin Daud, 2011).

In Malaysia, the government can sue or be sued. Section 3 of the Government Proceedings Act 1956 states:

“Subject to this Act and of any written law where the Government has a claim against any person which would, if such claim had arisen between subject and subject, afford ground for civil proceedings, the claim may be enforced by proceedings taken by or on behalf of the Government for that purpose in accordance with this Act.”

There are time limits to initiate an action against the government. According to section 2(a) Public Authorities Protection Act 1948, any proceeding against the government must be commenced within thirty-six months after the act neglect, or default complained of or, in the case of a continuance of injury or damage, within thirty-six months after the injury or damage has ceased. Section 2(a) states that:

“Where, after the coming into force of this Act, any suit, action, prosecution or other proceeding is commenced in the Federation against any person for any act done in pursuance or execution or intended execution of any written law or of any public duty or authority or in respect of any alleged neglect or default in the execution of any such written law, duty or authority the following provisions shall have effect-

(a) the suit, action, prosecution or proceeding shall not lie or be instituted unless it is commenced within thirty-six months next after the act neglect or default complained of, in the case of a continuance of injury or damage, within thirty-six months next after the ceasing thereof;”

Hence, the government may rely upon section 2(a) Public Authorities Protection Act 1948 as a defence, in any civil suits against the government for section 38 of the Government Proceedings Act 1956 states that, any written law relating to the limitation of time for bringing proceedings against public authorities may be relied upon by the government as a defence in any civil suits against the government.

It is noted that the liability of the government in tort is set out in section 5 of the Government Proceedings Act 1956, which states that:

“Subject to this Act, the Government shall be liable for any wrongful act done or any neglect or default committed by any public officer in the same manner and to the same extent as that in which a principal, being a private person, is liable for any wrongful act done, or any neglect or default committed by his agent, and for the purposes of this section and without prejudice to the generality thereof, any public officer acting or purporting in good faith to be acting in pursuance of a duty imposed by law shall be deemed to be the agent of and to be acting under the instructions of the Government.”

However, section 6 of the Government Proceedings Act 1956 limits the liability of the government as provided in section 5. Section 6 states that:

“(1) No proceedings shall lie against the Government by virtue of section 5 in respect of any act, neglect or default of any public officer, unless proceedings for damages in respect of such act, neglect or default would have lie against such officer personally.

(2) Any written law which negatives or limits the amount of the liability of any public officer in respect of any act, neglect or default committed by that officer shall, in the case of proceedings against the Government under section 5 in respect of such act, neglect or default of such officer, apply in relation to the Government as it would have applied in relation to such officer if the proceedings against the Government had been proceedings against such officer.

(3) No proceedings shall lie against the Government by virtue of section 5 in respect of anything done or omitted to be done by any person while discharging or purporting to discharge any responsibilities of a judicial nature vested in him, or any responsibilities which he has in connection with the execution of the judicial process.

(4) No proceedings shall lie against the Government by virtue of section 5 in respect of any act, neglect or default of any public officer, unless that officer was at the material time employed by the Government and paid in respect of his duties as an officer of the Government wholly out of the revenues of the Government, or any fund certified by the appropriate financial officer for the purposes of this subsection or was at the material time holding an office in respect of which the appropriate financial officer certifies that the holder thereof would normally be so paid.

(5) For the purposes of subsection (4) the expression “appropriate financial officer” means, in respect of the Federal Government, the Minister of Finance, and in respect of the Government of a State, the State Financial Officer, and, in the case of the States of Sabah and Sarawak, the State Minister responsible for finance.”

Any civil suits instituted by or against the federal government or a state government must be in the name of the government of Malaysia or the government of that state as the case may be. On top of that, all documents required to be served on the government for the purpose of or in connection with any civil suits by or against

the government may be served, in the case of proceedings by or against the federal government, on the Attorney General or such other officer as may be designated in that behalf, either generally or specially, by the Attorney General by notification in the gazette, and, in the case of proceedings by or against the government of a state, on the state secretary, and, in the case of the states of Sabah and Sarawak, on the state Attorney General of such state. (Order 73 rule 3(2) The Rules of Court 2012) (Hamid Sultan Bin Abu Backer, 2012).

5. RECENT JUDICIAL TRENDS

The judiciary plays an essential role in countering assault and custodial death. To understand judicial responses in civil suits arising out of assault and custodial death, the previous case laws decided in this area need to be studied. In doing so, 7 reported cases regarding civil suits arising out of assault and custodial death have been selected for deliberation. Although this study is confined to assault and death in custody, for the sake of discussion, cases concerning an assault by police outside of custody will also be considered. All the cases as set out below:

Case Name	Year	Type	Facts	Damages Awarded
Syarizan bin Sudirman (High Court)	2010	Assault during Arrest	The plaintiffs have suffered injuries fell from the motorcycle after kicked by police when he came abreast with the first plaintiff.	1 st Plaintiff – RM 536, 796.09 2 nd Plaintiff – RM4,250.00
Suzana bt Md Aris (High Court)	2011	Custodial Death	The deceased Mohd Anuar Bin Sharip had vomited blood whilst under detention but was denied proper medical care and attention.	RM1,537,220.00
N Indra a/p Nallathamby (High Court)	2013	Custodial Death	The deceased A. Kugan died in police custody. His body showed extensive injuries from beatings. (Case appealed to COA)	RM801,700.00 awarded by High Court. Reduced to RM701,700.00 at Court of Appeal
Datuk Seri Khalid bin Abu Bakar (Court of Appeal)	2015			
Nurasmira Maulat bt Abd Jaffar (Court of Appeal)	2014	Shot by Police	The deceased was shot when police approached his car for identification checking.	RM351,000.00
Vasanthi Maruthamuthu (High Court)	2014	Custodial Death	The deceased S. Ispanan died in police custody due to peritonitis as a result of perforation of the duodenum. He was denied proper medical care and attention.	Liability established. Damages to be assessed by SAR. Cost RM50,000 to Plaintiffs.
Mohd Hady bin Ya'akop (Court of Appeal)	2016	Assault in custody	The appellant was assaulted in custody and hospitalised for treatment as a result of injuries suffered from the assault.	RM210,100.00
Selvi a/p Narayan (High Court)	2017	Custodial Death	The deceased Chandran a/l Perumal died in police custody after being denied proper medical care and attention.	RM357,500.00

[The full citation of the above cases are as follows:

1. *Syarizan bin Sudirmin (A child claimed through the father and his attorney Sudirmin bin Selamat) & 2 Ors v Abdul Rahman bin Bukit & Anor* [2010] 3 AMR 561;
2. *Suzana bt Md Aris (claiming as administrator of the estate and a dependant of Mohd Anuar bin Sharip, deceased) v DSP Ishak bin Hussain & Ors* [2011] 1 MLJ 107;

3. *N Indra a/p Nallathamby (Administratrix of the Estate and Dependant of Kugan a/l Ananthan, deceased) v Datuk Seri Khalid bin Abu Bakar & Ors* [2013] MLJU 697;
4. *Nurasmira Maulat bt Abd Jaffar & 2 Ors v Ketua Polis Negara & 2 Ors* [2014] 6 AMR 661;
5. *Vasanthi Maruthamuthu & 4 Ors v Superintendan Azman Salim & Anor* [2014] 1 LNS 993;
6. *Datuk Seri Khalid bin Abu Bakar & Ors v N Indra a/p P Nallathamby (the administrator of the estate and dependent of Kugan a/l Ananthan, deceased) and another appeal* [2015] 1 MLJ 353;
7. *Mohd Hady bin Ya'akop v Hassan bin Marsom & 6 Ors* [2016] 4 AMR 326;
8. *Selvi a/p Narayan & Anor (Pentadbir bersama Estet dan tanggungan Chandran a/l Perumal, simati) v Koperal Zainal bin Mohd Ali & Ors* [2017] MLJU 11.]

From the cases reported above, the Courts have, especially in *Suzana's case* awarded substantial damages to the family. This shows the seriousness of the judicial response to this matter. These decisions have sent out a clear message that the judiciary will not tolerate members of PDRM who choose to act outside of the law. More so, Justice Lee Siew Seng in *Suzana's case*, Justice VT Singham in *Indra's case* and Justice S. Nantha Balan in *Selvi's case* have all made remarks that there should be zero tolerance towards deaths of detainees in police custody. The judiciary through case law has set the precedent that police brutality and disrespect for the law will not be tolerated.

6. CONCLUSION

The cases of assault and custodial death due to police brutality are a serious issue. Whenever assault and death occur in custody, it raises the public interest and attracts media attention. No doubt, the suspect and surviving family members have right to commence a civil suit seeking damages from the police officer and government over the assault and custodial death to demonstrate that the police officer and government entity should be held responsible for the wrongful act, but it is unclear whether or not the civil suit filed against the police officer and government do deter the widespread abuse in police department. However, one thing for sure, the substantial damages awarded by courts in the reported cases regarding assault and death in custody shows that the seriousness of the judicial response to this matter. These decisions have sent out a clear message to the police officers as a deterrent against future breaches.

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